

A Cross-cultural Study on the Relationship between Connectedness to Nature and the Psychological Well-being of Youth

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The present cross-cultural study examines the relationship between connectedness to nature and psychological well-being among young adults from two different geographical regions – metropolitan cities and regions with natural landscapes. The research aims to investigate how gender and current place of residence influence one's subjective connection to nature. The research employed a quantitative research design, and data were collected from youths of 18 to 29 years old. The study and findings suggest that both environmental and personal factors, such as gender and place of residence, may influence how young adults feel connected to nature.

Keywords: Connectedness to nature, psychological well-being, natural landscapes, metropolitan cities

Connectedness to nature indicates one's view of their own association with nature (Martin & Czellar, 2016). It indicates one's physical as well as psychological involvement with nature. Bonding with nature is found to reduce stress and anxiety, as well as increase the preference for green spaces (Chang et al., 2024). In a study, Cervinka et al. (2011) highlighted the significance of nature on health.

Zelenski et al. (2015) conducted three studies on how nature influences reflection and positive emotions. Participants took a 15-minute urban walk or watched urban and nature videos. Across all studies, nature exposure enhanced positive emotions, attention, nature connection, and self-reflection, with real nature having stronger effects than virtual nature. The analysis suggested that these benefits stem from a deeper sense of nature connectedness rather than improved attention.

Well-being has been defined as the combination of feeling good and functioning well; the experience of positive emotions such as happiness and contentment, as well as the development of one's potential, having some control over one's life, having a sense of purpose, and having positive relationships (Huppert, 2009).

Howell et al. (2011) discovered a significant link between nature and connectivity and psychological and social well-being. While natural connectedness was linked to well-being criteria other than life satisfaction and good affect, there was no significant relationship with emotional well-being. These findings were maintained even after correcting for social desirability biases, which is consistent with past mixed results in this field.

Psychological well-being includes positive experiences, including pleasure, fulfilment, and meaning. This idea covers

various aspects of mental and emotional health, such as positive relationships, personal growth, self-esteem, and a sense of control over one's life (Dhanabhakya & Sarath, 2023).

As with many multifaceted constructions, psychological well-being comprises various components that collectively contribute to an individual's overall sense of well-being:

- *Life Satisfaction:* refers to cognitive evaluations of one's life (Diener et al., 2002).
- Positive emotions, such as joy and contentment, which enhance resilience and overall happiness (Park & Peterson, 2006).
- *Negative Emotions:* such as sadness, anger, and anxiety, which may negatively impact well-being (Pam, 2013).
- *Autonomy:* is the ability to act independently and pursue personal goals (Waterman, 1993)
- *Positive Relationships:* social ties provide emotional support, a sense of community, and promote happiness and well-being (Park & Peterson, 2006)
- *Purpose in Life:* which offers direction and meaning, increasing contentment and happiness (Argyle, 1999; Sheldon & King, 2001).
- *Personal Growth:* continuous process of development and self-improvement r maintaining a sense of fulfilment and progress throughout life (Ryff, 1989; Diener et al., 1999).

A study conducted by Chang et al. (2024) found that people who have a stronger connection to nature benefit more from nature because there is a stronger correlation between their mental health score and their connection to nature. There are theories discussing how our connection to nature enhances our well-being:

Biophilia Hypothesis: This theory was given by Wilson in 1984. This theory implies that people are naturally drawn to nature and the natural world. The theory is based on the notion that a vital component of human well-being is our connection to nature, which has its roots in our revolutionary past. It therefore provides a framework for understanding the beneficial effects that nature can have on our health and well-being.

Attention Retention Theory: This theory was given by Rachel and Stephen Kaplan in their book 'The experience of nature: A psychological perspective' published in 1989. This theory suggests that spending time in nature or looking at it can help with mental fatigue and concentration.

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According to studies, both individual and environmental factors can have an impact on psychological well-being. Research has shown that personality qualities such as openness and conscientiousness are related to higher levels of well-being (Costa & McCrae, 1980). Individuals engaging in outdoor physical activity had lower somatic anxiety and higher Nature Relatedness Experience (Lawton et al., 2017).

With the ongoing modernisation and urbanisation, technology dependence has become a growing concern for young people as they are alienating themselves from nature. A study conducted by Mitchell (2013) found that regular use of natural environments for leisure activities has been linked to a lower risk of mental health issues. However, the link between natural environments and health outcomes may be more complex than previously thought.

This study will investigate whether a sense of connectedness to nature improves people's psychological well-being. The study also intends to look at young individuals from metropolitan cities and regions with natural landscapes to see if being in nature improves their psychological well-being. The goal is to compare the degree of connection to nature in both places to determine whether youths who live in more natural settings have higher psychological well-being than those who live in metropolitan cities. Previous research has identified the beneficial impact of nature on psychological well-being (for example, Nisbet et al., 2020; Mayer, 2015). However, there is a dearth of research from cross-sectional perspectives. Therefore, the present research addressed this gap by exploring the link between being connected to nature and psychological well-being from a cross-cultural perspective.

Objectives of the Study

- To determine the impact of connection with nature on the psychological well-being of youths.
- To determine the significance of cross-cultural factors on the psychological well-being of youth.

Operational Definition

- *Connectedness to Nature*: It refers to one's identification with nature.
- *Satisfaction with Life*: It can be described as a person's overall evaluation of how satisfied they are with their life.
- *Positive Affect*: It includes pleasant emotions such as happiness, excitement, and contentment.
- *Negative Affect*: It refers to the range of unpleasant emotions such as sadness, anger, anxiety, or stress.

Hypotheses of the Study

- *H0*: There is no significant difference between connectedness to nature and psychological well-being among genders of metropolitan cities and regions with natural landscapes.
- *H1*: There is a significant difference between connectedness to nature and psychological well-being among genders of metropolitan cities and regions with natural landscapes.
- *H0*: There is no significant difference in the levels of connectedness to nature between youths from Metropolitan cities and Regions with Natural Landscapes.
- *H1*: There is a significant difference in the levels of connectedness to nature between youths from Metropolitan cities and Regions with Natural Landscapes.
- *H0*: There is no significant difference in psychological well-being between youths from Metropolitan cities and Regions with

Natural Landscapes.

- *H1*: There is a significant difference in psychological well-being between youths from Metropolitan cities and Regions with Natural Landscapes.

Method

Participants

Sample size was 105, 59 from the metropolitan cities (male: 17; female: 42) and 46 from regions with natural landscapes (male: 21; female: 25). The sample was selected through purposive sampling.

Inclusion Criteria

- Young adults are between 18-29 years.
- Young adults from Metropolitan cities and Regions with Natural Landscapes.
- Individuals with a minimum educational qualification.

Exclusion Criteria

- Individuals below 18 years old.
- Individuals with any physical or psychological diagnosis.

Measures and Data Collection

Connectedness to Nature Scale (CNS): Connectedness to Nature Scale (CNS) is a 14-item tool developed by Mayer and Frantz. It is designed to measure an individual's emotional, experiential connection to nature, apart from cognitive beliefs about environmental sustainability.

Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS): The Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) is a 5-item tool developed by Diener et al. in 1985 to assess cognitive aspects of subjective well-being. It is widely used in scientific literature to measure life satisfaction.

Positive and Negative Schedule (PANAS): The Positive and Negative Schedule (PANAS) is a 20-item self-report questionnaire designed to assess an individual's recent emotional state, mainly focusing on positive and negative affect. As the questionnaire consists of 20 items, 10 items measure positive affect, and the other 10 items measure negative affect.

Procedure

- 105 youths were approached for the study.
- Informed consent was taken from them.
- The 3 questionnaires were administered through online mode, namely Connectedness to Nature Scale (CNS), Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) and Positive and Negative Schedule (PANAS).
- The data was then stored and coded in Microsoft excel before being analyzed with Jamovi (2.3.28).

Statistics

The statistical analysis methods to test these hypotheses include:

Shapiro Wilk Test: It helps to assess whether the data is normally distributed or deviates from normality.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA): It is used to test whether there are statistically significant differences between the means of three or more groups.

Results and Interpretation

The research aims to explore the relationship between connectedness to nature and psychological well-being among

youths. The study aimed to examine whether residence and gender significantly influenced connectedness to nature, satisfaction with life, and affective states.

Table 1A

Table Showing Tests of Normality Tests for Positive Affect, Negative Affect, Connectedness to Nature and Satisfaction with Life in Young Adults

Normality Test (Shapiro-Wilk) for Current Residence		
	W	P
Positive Affect	0.980	0.111
Negative Affect	0.987	0.372
CNS	0.989	0.581
SWLS	0.985	0.299

Normality Test (Shapiro-Wilk) for Gender		
	W	P
Positive Affect	0.979	0.100
Negative Affect	0.987	0.396
CNS	0.988	0.485
SWLS	0.984	0.229

The Shapiro-Wilk was conducted to assess the normality of the variables Positive Affect, Negative Affect, Connectedness to Nature (CNS), and Satisfaction with Life (SWLS) across current residence and gender. Since all the p-values are greater than 0.05, the assumption or normality is met.

Table 1B

Homogeneity of Variance (Levene's) Positive Affect, Negative Affect, Connectedness to Nature and Satisfaction with Life in Young Adults

Homogeneity of Variances Test (Levene's) for Current residence				
	F	df1	df2	p
Positive Affect	0.3358	1	104	0.564
Negative Affect	2.6826	1	104	0.104
CNS	0.0365	1	104	0.849
SWLS	1.0444	1	104	0.309

Homogeneity of Variances Test (Levene's) for Gender				
	F	df1	df2	p
Positive Affect	3.03933	1	103	0.084
Negative Affect	0.00626	1	103	0.937
CNS	0.46689	1	103	0.496
SWLS	2.65711	1	103	0.106

Table 2C

Showing the Interaction Effect of Gender and Current Residence on Connectedness to Nature

Gender	Current residence	Mean	Standard Deviation	F	p
Female	Metropolitan cities	52.4	7.28	0.9957	0.321
	Regions with natural landscapes	50.9	6.10		
Male	Metropolitan cities	49.2	5.03		
	Regions with natural landscapes	50.4	7.10		

The table presents the interaction effect of gender and current residence on connectedness to nature. The data shows that females living in metropolitan cities reported a slightly higher score ($M =$

Levene's Test of Homogeneity of Variances was used to assess whether the variances of Positive Affect, Negative Affect, Connectedness to nature (CNS), and Satisfaction with Life are equal across different groups. Since all p-values are greater than 0.05, it indicates that the assumption is met.

Table 2A

Showing the Mean, Standard Deviation, ANOVA value and Significant of Connectedness to Nature for Current Residence

		Mean	Standard Deviation	F	p
Current residence	Metropolitan cities	51.4	6.82	0.0167	0.897
	Regions with Natural landscapes	50.7	6.50		

The table provides the results of comparison of the mean scores of the current residence of the participants. The mean score for participants from metropolitan cities was 51.4 with a standard deviation of 6.82, while those from natural landscapes had a mean score of 50.7 and a standard deviation of 6.50. In order to determine its statistical significance, ANOVA was conducted, and the analysis yielded an F-value of 0.0167 and a p-value of 0.897. Since the p-value is higher than the accepted level of significance ($p > 0.05$), the result is not statistically significant.

Therefore, it can be concluded that current residence does not have a significant effect on connectedness to nature.

Table 2B

Showing the Mean, Standard Deviation, ANOVA value and Significance of Connectedness to Nature for Gender

		Mean	Standard Deviation	F	p
Gender	Female	52.4	7.28	1.7594	0.188
	Male	49.2	5.03		

The table provides the results of a comparison of the mean scores of the gender of participants. The mean scores of females are 52.4 with a standard deviation of 7.28, whereas males have a slightly lower mean score of 49.2 and a standard deviation of 5.03. The ANOVA test conducted yielded an F-value of 1.7594 and a p-value of 0.188. Since the p-value is greater than the accepted level of significance ($p > 0.05$), the result is not statistically significant.

Therefore, gender does not have a significant influence on connectedness to nature.

52.4, $SD = 7.28$) compared to females living in regions with natural landscapes ($M = 50.9, SD = 6.10$). On the other hand, male participants from nature-oriented regions have scored higher ($M =$

50.4, $SD = 7.10$) as compared to males from metropolitan cities ($M = 49.2$, $SD = 5.03$). However, the ANOVA results reflect that the interaction between gender and current residence is not statistically

significant, as F -value = 0.9957, p -value = 0.321 is greater than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$).

Table 3A

Showing the Mean, Standard Deviation, ANOVA value and Significance of Satisfaction with Life for Current Residence

		Mean	Standard Deviation	F	p
Current residence	Metropolitan cities	4.68	3.98	0.349	0.556
	Regions with Natural landscapes	5.11	4.59		

The table presents a comparison of satisfaction with life between individuals residing in metropolitan cities and those in regions with natural landscapes. Participants from natural landscapes reported a higher mean score ($M = 5.11$, $SD = 4.59$) compared to those from metropolitan cities ($M = 4.68$, $SD = 3.98$). The ANOVA test results showed that the difference is not statistically significant ($F = 0.349$, $p = 0.556$).

Hence, current residence does not have a significant effect on the participants' satisfaction with life.

The table provides a comparison of satisfaction with life scores between male and female participants. The mean scores for females were slightly higher ($M = 21.2$, $SD = 7.28$) than compared for males

($M = 20.8$, $SD = 5.03$). An ANOVA test was conducted, which yielded a result of $F = 0.349$, $p = 0.556$, showing that the difference is not statistically significant, as the p -value is above 0.05.

Table 3B

Showing the Mean, Standard Deviation, ANOVA value and Significant of Satisfaction with Life for Gender

		Mean	Standard Deviation	F	p
Gender	Female	21.2	7.28	1.331	0.251
	Male	20.8	5.03		

It can be concluded that gender does not significantly influence satisfaction with life.

Table 3C

Showing the Interaction Effect of Gender and Current Residence on Satisfaction with Life

Gender	Current residence	Mean	Standard Deviation	F	p
Female	Metropolitan cities	21.2	5.11	0.565	0.454
	Regions with natural landscapes	20.8	4.59		
Male	Metropolitan cities	20.8	4.68		
	Regions with natural landscapes	20.7	3.3		

The table presents the interaction effect of gender and current residence on satisfaction with life. The data shows that females living in metropolitan cities reported a slightly higher score ($M = 21.2$, $SD = 5.11$) compared to females living in regions with natural landscapes ($M = 20.8$, $SD = 4.59$). On the other hand, male participants from

metropolitan cities have scored higher ($M = 20.8$, $SD = 4.68$) as compared to males from nature nature-oriented region ($M = 20.7$, $SD = 3.3$). However, the ANOVA results reflect that the interaction between gender and current residence is not statistically significant, as F -value = 0.565, p -value = 0.454 is greater than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$).

Table 4A

Showing the Mean, Standard Deviation, ANOVA value and Significant of Positive Affect for Current Residence

		Mean	Standard Deviation	F	p
Current residence	Metropolitan cities	32.0	8.05	0.0704	0.791
	Regions with Natural landscapes	32.7	7.20		

The table presents a comparison of positive affect scores with respect to the participants' current residence. The results indicate that individuals living in natural surroundings reported a slightly higher mean score ($M = 32.7$, $SD = 7.20$) for positive affect compared to those living in metropolitan areas ($M = 32.0$, $SD = 8.05$). The ANOVA test produced an F -value of 0.00222 and a p -value = 0.963,

which indicates that the difference is not statistically significant since the p -value is higher than 0.05.

Therefore, the results of this study imply that the physical environment does not have a significant influence on positive affect among individuals.

Table 4B

Showing the Mean, Standard Deviation, ANOVA value and Significant of Positive Affect with Life for Gender

		Mean	Standard Deviation	F	p
Gender	Female	32.1	8.03	0.1112	0.740
	Male	32.6	6.25		

The table presents a comparison of positive affect scores with

respect to the participants' current residence. The results indicate that males reported a higher mean score ($M = 32.6, SD = 6.25$) for positive affect compared to females ($M = 32.1, SD = 8.03$). The ANOVA test produced an F-value of 0.15328 and a p-value = 0.697 which indicates that the difference is not statistically significant since the p value is higher than 0.05.

Therefore, the results of this study imply that gender does not have a significant influence on positive affect among individuals.

Table 4C

Showing the Interaction Effect of Gender and Current Residence on Positive Affect

Gender	Current residence	Mean	Standard Deviation	F	p
Female	Metropolitan cities	32.1	8.34	5.50	0.981
	Regions with natural landscapes	32.5	8.03		
Male	Metropolitan cities	32.6	7.19		
	Regions with natural landscapes	33.0	6.25		

The table illustrates the interaction effect of gender and current residence on positive affect. The mean scores indicate that individuals residing in regions with natural landscapes reported slightly higher positive affect compared to those living in metropolitan cities, with males in natural areas showing the highest

average score ($M=33.0, SD = 6.25$) and females in metropolitan cities showing the lowest ($M = 32.1, SD = 8.34$). The results of the two-way ANOVA reveal that the interaction between gender and current residence is not statistically significant, $F = 5.50, p\text{-value} = 0.981$ which is higher than the standard p-value.

Table 5A

Showing the Mean, Standard Deviation, ANOVA value and Significance of Negative Affect for Current Residence

		Mean	Standard Deviation	F	p
Current residence	Metropolitan cities	29.1	8.26	0.00222	0.963
	Regions with Natural landscapes	28.2	9.75		

The table represents the comparison of negative scores between the individuals living in metropolitan cities and those in regions surrounded by natural landscapes. The results reveal that participants living in metropolitan cities reported high scores in negative affect ($M = 29.1, SD = 8.26$) compared to those living in nature-oriented environments ($M = 28.2, SD = 9.75$). ANOVA tests reveal an F-value of 0.00222 and a p-value of 0.963, which are higher than standard p-value 0.05. So, it implies that the difference is not significant.

Hence, there is no significant difference to conclude the influence of one's natural residential setting on negative affect.

The table represents the comparison of negative scores between the males and females. The results reveal that females reported high scores in negative affect ($M = 30.3, SD = 7.28$) compared to those

living in nature-oriented environments ($M = 26.8, SD = 5.03$). ANOVA tests reveal an F-value of 0.15238 and a p-value of 0.697 which are higher than standard p-value 0.05. So, it implies that the difference is not significant.

Table 5B

Showing the Mean, Standard Deviation, ANOVA value and Significant of Negative Affect with Life for Gender

		Mean	Standard Deviation	F	p
Gender	Female	30.0	7.28	0.15238	0.697
	Male	26.8	5.03		

There is no significant difference to conclude the influence of one's gender on negative affect.

Table 5C

Showing the Interaction Effect of Gender and Current Residence on Negative Affect

Gender	Current residence	Mean	Standard Deviation	F	p
Female	Metropolitan cities	30.0	8.12	1.91435	0.170
	Regions with natural landscapes	27.4	10.3		
Male	Metropolitan cities	26.8	8.59		
	Regions with natural landscapes	29.2	9.25		

The table illustrates the interaction effect of gender and current residence on negative affect. Females living in metropolitan cities have reported the highest mean score of 30.3 with an SD of 8.12. As per the male counterparts, males residing in regions with natural landscapes have scored higher ($M = 29.2$, $SD = 9.25$) compared to males residing in metropolitan cities ($M = 26.8$, $SD = 8.59$). For females living in nature-oriented regions have scored lower negative affect ($M = 27.4$, $SD = 10.3$). However, the interaction effect between gender and current residence on negative affect was found to be statistically non-significant ($F = 1.91435$, p -value = 0.170).

Discussion

The study investigated the association between connectedness to nature and psychological well-being among young adults aged 18 to 29 from metropolitan cities and regions with natural landscapes. The aim of the study was to examine whether an individual's environmental surroundings and gender have a significant influence on levels of connectedness to nature and psychological well-being. The study emphasised 105 youths aged 18-29 years old. 59 (42 female and 17 male) participants and 46 (25 female & 21 male) participants took part in this study.

The findings showed no significant difference in connectedness to nature between young people living in cities and those in natural areas. Although it was expected that individuals living near nature would feel more connected, the average scores for both groups were nearly the same (Metropolitan cities: $M = 51.4$, Natural landscapes: $M = 50.7$). The study also found no meaningful differences in connectedness to nature based on gender. Female participants had slightly higher average scores compared to males, but the difference was not significant enough to indicate a real effect. This supports earlier research by Howell et al. (2011) which showed that while patterns in emotional or environmental sensitivity exist, they do not always lead to significant differences in nature connection.

Overall, the study did not find any significant differences in connectedness to nature or psychological well-being and its components.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be observed that the present research did not observe any significant cross-cultural impact on the youth's psychological well-being, nor did not identify any significant impact of connectedness to nature on the youth's psychological well-being.

Implications of the Study

With respect to this study, it highlights that in the upcoming development of planning health policies, they should ensure easy access to green spaces and build more nature-based recreational infrastructure in cities. Not only that, but education systems should promote fostering an environment that may also improve the well-being of the students.

Awareness campaigns should be promoted to help youths as well as people understand the importance of engaging in nature, which helps them build a stronger connection to nature and develop healthier coping strategies.

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